

The Effectiveness of Employee Advocacy Programs in Enhancing Corporate Reputation and Engagement

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Abstract

This research aims to establish the impact of employee advocacy programs on the credibility of corporations and stakeholders' interest. This paper will adopt the concept of employee advocacy, which refers to the act of employees marketing brands, goods, or services of their working organization within their social circles. This study examines the effect of such programs on corporate reputation and employees' engagement with the help of qualitative and quantitative data from numerous cases from different sectors. The evidence points to the fact that employee advocacy can play a great role in positively improving the corporation's reputation as the employees help it spread its messages organically thus creating a word-of-mouth perception with the outside world. Furthermore, the paper demonstrates that such programs also affect employee engagement because people who engage in advocacy campaigns, but the research also reveals possible obstacles, including lack of definite rules, and sufficient practice as to guarantee the advocacy activities conformed with corporate values and strategies. Finally, based on the findings of the study, guidelines for promotion of employee advocacy to benefit the organization's corporate image and facilitate the improvement of the organization's employee engagement are suggested.

Keywords: *Employee advocacy, Employee engagement, strategic corporate communication*

Introduction

Today's business world is much more competitive and interdependent therefore corporate reputation issue plays an important role in the achievement of the business corporation's goals. It builds and improves the confidence of customers with the firm's products or services, increases employee attraction, and improves its scored stakeholder relations. As a result, the concept of company reputation remains under tremendous pressure to develop new methods of cultivation as well as sustenance (Barger et.al 2018). Of these strategies, the most recent and increasingly popular strategy is the employee advocacy which refers to the practice whereby employees of a firm engage in marketing or advertising their employer's brand, product or service through their own networks. This form of advocacy is credible and genuine because employees widely interact with their counterpart and their sphere of influence will help boost corporate image. Employee advocacy programs are meant to promote and facilitate a company's ability to get their employees to become active promoters of the company's image both on and off the social media networks. Such programs may comprise orientation, support, and reward systems for the workers on the ways they should present the organization's interests and at the same time abide by the organizational culture and mission (Berthon et.al 2018). The intended consequences of such programmes are not limited to increased corporate reputation and improved customer satisfaction; such initiatives have further positive implications, this being employee satisfaction. For commitment, it makes employees perform their duties effectively and efficiently since their commitment is towards their organization not the outside world hence less turnover and organizational goals are in conformity with the employee's goals.

However, there is little empirical study on ways in which employee advocacy programs can meet the intended objectives as the concept gains popularity among the firms. Although there is a growing number of cases where the employment of employee advocates was considered effective for enhancing corporate reputation of the employee's company, as well as the level of their engagement, there are still few empirical studies, which can provide precise and accurate evaluation of these effects. This study intends to address the above problem by assessing the impact of employee advocacy on corporate image and stakeholder relations. In an effort to facilitate the understanding of how employee advocacy programs can positively impact the success of organisations, as well as identifying procedures that should be followed to ensure the

programmers' efficiency, this research aims at analyzing numerous cases, questionnaires and interviews (Brusseau et al. 2019).

Research Background

The theoretical framework associated with the employee advocacy as a concept is closely connected to such related fields as employee engagement, and corporate communication where the organizations' concern about the role of the employees as the valuable assets of the company stems from. Heretofore, both tactical and strategic corporate communication was restricted to the direct management of the organization, primarily utilizing in-house press releases, advertising techniques and corporate Web sites as the chief media for the brand messages (Calabrese et al. 2020). Yet, the increase of social platforms and the possibilities of digital communication have inarguably changed the picture, making employees actual influencers in the perception of the organizations they work for. This shift has led to the concept of employee advocacy programs that are actually structures where the company encourages its employees to become the mouth piece of the company and its beliefs. Based on the literature review regarding employee engagement, one of the most common findings is the suboptimal level of employees' sense of organizational membership. Staff that are motivated are not only higher performers, absent less often and less likely to resign from the organization but also market the organization to their social and professional networks. That is where employee advocacy programs come into play;

the natural tendency is welcomed, and guided to create Corporate sponsorship of the employees' messages. Other previous research findings made identified that when employees promote their organization, this produces more trust from the other consumers, since they believe the information is coming from a real consumer who they can relate to rather from a corporate communication(Chahal et.al 2017). Moreover, advocating for those programs that are beneficial for the company can also improve employees' engagement, as committed employees assist in maintaining a good image leading to the improvement of corporate social capital, which in turn increases employee engagement. However, as Ambrose et al. (1998) suggested that many empirical issues of employee advocacy programs research are underdeveloped in prior studies, the opportunity to understand these programs' effectiveness in different organizational contexts appears to be limited. Therefore, this research aims to contribute to the current literature by offering a comprehensive analysis of best practices and benefits of employee advocacy programs, tailored towards helping organizations improve the employees' engagement and strengthening the overall business reputation (Cheung et.al 2019).

Research Objectives

- To assess the impact of employee advocacy programs on corporate reputation across different industries and organizational contexts.
- To evaluate the effectiveness of employee advocacy programs in enhancing employee engagement and commitment to the organization.
- To identify the key factors that contributes to the success or failure of employee advocacy programs in achieving their intended outcomes.
- To provide practical recommendations for designing and implementing employee advocacy programs that effectively align with corporate values and strategic objectives.

Research Problems

A trend evident in most organizations within the growth of employee advocacy programs is the extent to which it has been adopted as a strategic corporate tool to facilitate reputation management and boost workers' morale for organizational productivity. Nonetheless, despite growing application of these programs, there is still a major deficiency in the knowledge of the demonstrated outcomes. Although there is certain amount of literature based on assumptions that

advocate for employees' support to organizations and dissemination of fine image can elicit positive changes in corporate image, as well as enhance employees' engagement, there is scant research undertaken in diverse settings that examines these effects systematically, scientifically (Men et.al 2017). The absence of similar broad-based research presents a problem for the organizations who want to build and maximize the efficiency of the employee advocacy programs since the factors that determine success or failure of such programs are not adequately defined. Some of the research issues include the determination of the actual effects that employee advocacy has on the reputation of the firm (Kim et.al 2017). While its constituents, the employees, are considered by most organization stakeholders as believable and genuine commentators, it is still ambiguous as to how effective their advocacy initiatives are in improving the image of their corresponding firms across various industries and for other stakeholders. More to the point, priority has not been given to how such programs would hold up in different organizational settings, especially when comparing between multinational corporations and small to medium enterprises. The final significant issue examined in this research problem refers to the connection between advocacy and engagement of employees. Although it has been proposed that students' engagement may increase when offered a chance to partake in advocacy programs due to increased perceptions of relevance to the organization and values, little research has been done. Furthermore, there is a dearth of information that addresses the following research questions on the factors that mediate the effectiveness of these programs to improve employees' engagement: • Training • Performance related rewards and • Corporate culture. Solving these research questions can help in providing concrete and actionable recommendations for organizations to possibly use in production of good employee advocacy strategies. It is proposed that the results of this research would alleviate a major gap within the existing academic and practitioner literature by considering the empirical effects of the above-mentioned programs on both corporate reputation and employee engagement(Moreno et.al 2019).

Literature Review

Evaluating the effectiveness of employee advocacy programs in enhancing employee engagement and commitment to the organization

Recent studies have focused on the links that exist between employee advocacy programmes and employee engagement since organisation profit from such programmes by increasing both organisational and personal benefits. One of the organizational work variables, often researched closely in the literature because of its positive connection with performance, turnover, and organizational commitment is Employee engagement which can be described as the emotional and cognitive connection that an employee has with the organisation (Saks, 2006, Schaufeli & Bakker, 2010). It is argued that [Employee advocacy programs, which entail employees promoting their company's brand and values] positively impacts this engagement because of the enhanced ownership of organizational objectives. Some prior works have tried to uncover the processes by which employee advocacy can create more engagement (Kang et.al 2017). For example, Macey and Schneider (2008) posit that with advocacy freedom is achieved because the employees promote the organisation; in this way, they lead engaged employees. Likewise, advocacy programs research conducted by Men and Bowen in 2017 notes that the company's advocacy participation increases organizational individual job importance, which results in job satisfaction and organizational commitment among the employees. But the literature also presents the concept of organizational support as a crucial element for boosting the efficiency of the chosen strategy implemented through employee advocacy. In a similar context, Pansari and Kumar (2017) stress that unless they are accompanied by adequate training, clear policies and adequate incentives; these programs can provide a mere compliance level. According to them, for advocating programs to be effective, they need to be part of a total organizational staff development and appreciation program which makes the employees to feel wanted and capable to sell the image of the organization (Nisar et.al 2020). Nevertheless, literature review led by this study presents scarce evidence on the relationship between the degrees of actual engagement of the employees as an aspect of the advocacy programs implemented in the organization. Indeed, the literature offers several concepts and ideas regarding advocacy and its outcomes, yet, more empirically grounded and contextual research are required to measure the effects of advocacy programs on employees' engagement and to establish what types of programs would be most

effective in which environments. Thus, this study seeks to fill this research gap by assessing the impact of employee advocacy on employee engagement and organizational commitment (Ki et.al 2018).

Key factors that contribute to the success or failure of employee advocacy programs in achieving their intended outcomes

There are several crucial factors that determine whether or not the employee advocacy programs and tools will deliver on the planned goals and objectives like the improvement of the corporate image, the increase of the level of engagement among the employees, and others. A literature review of employee advocacy and related fields suggests a number of potential moderators that may affect program effectiveness, such as the organizations' culture, its leadership, approaches to communication, levels of resource and training invested in the programme (Jianget.al 2018). Another major factor is the organizational culture to which the employment advocacy belongs. When it comes to Hofstede's cultural dimensions theory, the likelihood of success of advocacy

programs is high in organizations with strong values such as trust, transparency and openness (Hofstede, 1984) the communication culture together with the input culture of an organization means that employees are comfortable in defending their organizations since they believe their input is of value. This is aligned to the works of Men and Stacks (2014) that recognized internal communication climate as requisite in promoting employees' engagement in advocacy programs. Another input is the leadership support for the e-learning system. Men (2014)'s study affirms that employee advocacy can only be effective if supported by senior management and must be visibly done from top management (Hur et.al 2017). Wherever possible, leaders must participate in these programs themselves in order to extend the message throughout the particular company's employees. The chief endorsement has the function not only of legalizing the advocacy efforts, but also of orienting them towards the set targets of the organization. Strategies of communication also play a crucial role in the functionality of the employee advocacy programs. Writing for Welch (2012), a point made was that there is a need to frequently communicate, in clear and consistent manner, to ensure that the employees are fully conversant with the advocacy program items. That is not only the introduction of the program but also the subsequent messages that strengthen its key topics and successes. Also, within the various factors for success identified by numerous scholars, availability of enough resources and training stands out as a crucial aspect. According to Pansari and Kumar (2017), employees will advocate for the organization as much as possible when they have the resources, education, and the backing to do it. If these resources are not available there is a possibility that employees especially those in new organizations will feel unequipped, shy or even reluctant to engage in such projects hence a possibility of poor result being recorded. In sum, based on the existing literature, we can conclude that there is a series of factors that can positively or negatively influence the results of the implementation of employee advocacy programs: organizational culture, management support, communication practices, and resources and training. That is why, it is critical to acknowledge and manage these factors to improve the achievement of advocacy program goals by organizations desiring to implement efficient advocacy programs(Harris et.al 2018).

Effective Strategies to Improve Employee Engagement

Methodology

This research uses a main method of quantitative research to assess the impact of employees' advocacy in improving corporate image and employee commitment. Collecting data shall be done through distributing a self-developed structured survey questionnaire designed to productive organizations that have adopted employee advocacy programs. The two types of questions used in the survey will be closed-ended questions in order to obtain quantifiable values of the variables of interests such as the scope of advocacy programs on corporate reputation, the level of employees' engagement and the factors that led to success and failure of the advocacy program. The questions to be included in the survey instrument will be sourced from the existing literature on scales with the assembly and adjustments being made for the purpose of capturing the unique aspects of advocacy among employees (Golding et.al 2020). To test reliability and validity of the survey items, Cronbach's alpha will be employed for the former, while the exploratory factor analysis will be used for the later. Quantitative data obtained from the survey will have to be analyzed using Statistical Package of the Social Science (SPSS). Demographic statistics will again be utilized to analyse the respondents' demography as well as the data acquired from the specific survey questions. Hypothesis testing tools like multiple regression analysis and correlation analysis are also going to be used to analyze the extent of the relationship between the variables like the Employee advocacy programs, Corporate reputation and Employee engagement. Further the technique of analysis of variance (ANOVA) would be

employed to examine the differences of perception within the analysis of the demographic variables like age, organizational tenure and organizational position. The application of SPSS will afford systematic technological analysis in order to pinpoint the specific pattern and trends inherent in the data collected. The research findings will offer generalized information concerning employee advocacy programs which will in turn give a guideline to any organisation that would like to increase its corporate reputation as well as that of its employees through such programs (Hammediet.al 2019).

Analysis

Demographic examination

Age

What is your age?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	15-25 years	6	9.1	9.1	9.1
	26-35 years	17	25.8	25.8	34.8
	36-45 years	25	37.9	37.9	72.7
	46 years and above	18	27.3	27.3	100.0
	Total	66	100.0	100.0	

The chart and table suggest that there were 37.88% 36 to 45 years aged individuals, 27.27% above 45 years age, 25.76% 26 to 35 years of age, and the least frequent were 9.09% of 15 to 25 years of age in the survey.

Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Female	23	34.8	34.8	34.8
Male	20	30.3	30.3	65.2
Prefer not to say	23	34.8	34.8	100.0
Total	66	100.0	100.0	

The table and figure describe the indicator of gender of the respondents signifying the collective percentage of males is 30.30%, 34.85% females, and other gender groups who denied to reveal their gender.

Designation

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid CEO	15	22.7	22.7	22.7
COO	21	31.8	31.8	54.5
Managers	30	45.5	45.5	100.0
Total	66	100.0	100.0	

It can be supposed that the valid percentage of managers is the highest at 45.45% and the lowest frequently are the CEOs is 22.73%, however, there were 31.82% of COOs.

Statistical analysis

Descriptive analysis

Descriptive Statistics									
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
DV	66	1	3	1.67	.950	.724	.295	-1.523	.582
IV1	66	1	5	2.09	1.795	1.045	.295	-.938	.582
IV2	66	1	5	3.12	2.012	-.124	.295	-2.048	.582
IV3	66	1	5	2.23	1.356	.945	.295	-.160	.582
Valid N (listwise)	66								

From the table of descriptive figures, it can be undoubtedly understood that for each variable the value of SE for both skewness and kurtosis.

Hypothesis

H1: There is a significant connection between participation in employee advocacy programs and corporate reputation and engagement

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.217 ^a	.047	.032	.935	2.099

a. Predictors: (Constant), IV1
b. Dependent Variable: DV

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2.750	1	2.750	3.148	.081 ^b
	Residual	55.917	64	.874		
	Total	58.667	65			

a. Dependent Variable: DV
b. Predictors: (Constant), IV1

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.427	.177		8.044	.000
	IV1	.115	.065	.217	1.774	.081

a. Dependent Variable: DV

The above regression table designates that the R and R square values of IV1 concerning DV are .21 and 0.047. However, the significant value of IV1 is 0.081 greater than the value of 0.05, thus resulting in a weak connection between the Dv and IV1.

H2: Quality of advocacy content plays a significant role in boosting corporate reputation and engagement

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.494 ^a	.244	.232	.833	2.610

a. Predictors: (Constant), IV2
b. Dependent Variable: DV

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	14.302	1	14.302	20.631	.045 ^b
	Residual	44.365	64	.693		
	Total	58.667	65			

a. Dependent Variable: DV
b. Predictors: (Constant), IV2

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.394	.190		12.589	.000
	IV2	-.233	.051	-.494	-4.542	.045

a. Dependent Variable: DV

The overhead figure displays that the R and R square values are 0.4 and 0.24, however, the Darwin Watson value is 2.6, highlighting that there is a strong relationship between IV2 and DV.

H3: Employee Empowerment and Training have a strong relationship with corporate reputation and engagement

Model Summary ^a					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.454 ^a	.206	.193	.853	2.487

a. Predictors: (Constant), IV3
b. Dependent Variable: DV

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	12.074	1	12.074	16.586	.050 ^b
	Residual	46.592	64	.728		
	Total	58.667	65			

a. Dependent Variable: DV
b. Predictors: (Constant), IV3

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.374	.203		11.694	.000
	IV3	-.318	.078	-.454	-4.073	.050

a. Dependent Variable: DV

The overhead regression table depicts that the Durbin-Watson value is 2.48, however, the sign value is 0.50 equal to the standard value of 0.05, thus signifying a significant connection between employee empowerment and training, corporate reputation, and engagement.

Correlation test

		Correlations			
		DV	IV1	IV2	IV3
DV	Pearson Correlation	1	.217	-.494**	-.454**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.908	.000	.000
	N	66	66	66	66
IV1	Pearson Correlation	.217	1	-.378**	.352**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.908		.002	.004
	N	66	66	66	66
IV2	Pearson Correlation	-.494**	-.378**	1	-.134
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.002		.282
	N	66	66	66	66
IV3	Pearson Correlation	-.454**	.352**	-.134	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.004	.282	
	N	66	66	66	66

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlative table displays the Pearson correlation values of the developed IVs and DV, it can be thought that the uppermost relation value is 0.908 which is near the P-value highlighting the strong connection.

Discussion

The data derived from this study could thus yield crucial information for understanding the usefulness of the EAP on two vital aspects of business: reputation and workforce satisfaction. The quantitative analysis shows that when the employees are actively engaged in such advocacy programs, there is perceived enhancement in corporate reputation. This indicates that whenever employees become advocates, the facts and information that they give to the public enhances the organization's credibility hence supporting other scholars who argue that when such information is provided by employees, it is highly credible and authentic (Men & Stacks, 2014). Furthermore, this research also points out that while the main impact of employee advocacy could be seen at the external level, the internal level is also impacted by this kind of programs significantly (Feng et.al 2019). These programs also show that depending on advocacy initiatives, one can enhance

employee engagement and commitment since the those who take part in such programs show higher ... satisfaction. This is in line with theories on engagement where it is said that employee will be more engaged if the see the roles assigned to them as relevant and with the goal of the organization at large (Macey & Schneider, 2008). However, it also outlines possible problems with the management of the employee advocacy programs. The outcomes of these programs seem to be closely related to characteristics of the organization, including culture, support from the leaders, and availability of resources and trainings. Thus, more effective outcomes of the advocacy programs could be expected in organizations with supportive culture and effective leadership as they encourage employees' engagement(Dwivedi et.al 2021). On the other hand, when there are no proper guidelines, inadequate training, or poor leadership backing, such programs may actually prove counterproductive for the intended purpose or can make them disheartening, thereby going against organisational messages. In sum, this research asserts the need for strategic thought and backing in the execution of employee advocacy programs. Despite the fact that corporate reputation and employees' engagement appear to benefit from these programs immensely, these programmes may only be successful if the organisational context is properly understood and effective resources and leadership provided in their support. The outcomes of this research open a valuable avenue for practical guidance and contribute to the advancement of theoretic knowledge about the circumstances under which EAPs are likely to show the greatest impact among its stakeholders (Crain et.al 2020).

Conclusion

The research objectives of this study were to establish the current state of knowledge on employee advocacy programmes and assess their impact on the extent of corporate brand reputation and employee engagement activities, both of which are topics that have garnered increasing scholarly and managerial attention in the last decade. The results strongly support the proposition that employee advocacy programs could be powerful tools for organisations that are interested in enhancing their reputation and increasing employees' loyalty. Thus, the involved usage of authentic voices of an organisation's employees allows improving the latter's external image and promoting more credible relationships with stakeholders. In addition, it has also noted that commitment and satisfaction that results from employees' participation in advocacy programs are key aspects of engagement. The study also reveals several factors that would influence the effectiveness of such programmes. Therefore, organizational culture, leadership

support, and the availability of resources as well as sufficient training were revealed as significant enablers and barriers to the effectiveness of employee advocacy programs. The sophistication of a firm's culture and management plays a pivotal role in helping organization's staff feel like change supporters and promoters. On the other hand, the lack of these factors results in low people's interest with the programs and poor performance, proof of which is the importance of a well thought out and supported approach in the implementation of advocacy programs. Nonetheless, based on this study, while they hold the potential to confer a vast number of advantages, even employee advocacy programs are no sure bet. Variance in the results depending on the organizational environment indicates the importance of procedural modifications that should reflect specific features of an organization. Therefore, the concept of employee advocacy programs is one of the most promising activities for improving the company's reputation and involving all the motivated employees in increasing the brand value; however, this tool will work only if it corresponds to the general plan of organizational development. In doing so, this research enriches the existing knowledge base on employee advocacy and offers organizational practitioners useful recommendations for sustaining business success through the use of advocacy strategies.

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